

**SUCSESSES AND SHORTCOMINGS OF USING MODERN
TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH**

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Abstract: The application of modern technology represents a significant advance in all spheres of human life. The use of innovation technologies is playing a big role in education also, especially in teaching foreign languages like English. Without any doubt, there are some pros and cons of this issue which will be discussed in the article below.

Key words: IT, education, teaching English, interactive methods.

Modern technology changed the whole things what people saw in the last decades. New machines, gadgets and devices are invented to make jobs easier like never done before. Innovations made it also easier for students, teachers and learners to extract the possibilities of the latest tech inventions. Their influence is enormous in crafting perfect generation expertise in the current technology. Besides that, technology has profoundly impacted almost every aspect of our lives, and education is no exception. In many ways, one might think that education hasn't changed much over the recent years. The first thing which should be taken into consideration is the whole change of lesson process. To be more specific, teachers in the pre-technological period did not have enough tools to enhance their teaching process. They depended mostly on the blackboard and the chalk to make the lesson more interesting, make the topic easier to understand and enjoyable for the students. Being the main source of information, teachers stood at the center of the auditory or classroom, having lectures and explaining theme orally while students passively listened it. However, in recent decades, in the world of information technologies the classrooms changed from teacher-centered to student-centered. This change had a great impact on the teaching process and its effectiveness.

As it is mentioned above, there some basic advantages and disadvantages of the usage of technologies in the process of teaching languages especially, second or third language. On the one hand, "...language is the most important means of communication, the existence and development of human society is impossible without it. The current changes in social relations, communication means (the use of new information technologies) require increasing the communicative competence of students, improving their philological preparation. In order they could exchange their thoughts in different situations in the process of interaction with other communicators, using the system of language and speech norms and choosing communicative behavior adequate to the authentic situation of communication. ... Modern technologies of teaching foreign languages accumulate successful information of each of them; enable the teacher to adjust any technology in accordance with the structure, functions, content, goals and objectives of training in the particular group of students.

The long-term practice of teaching English proves that teaching with traditional technologies does not allow developing key, basic competencies in a particular academic discipline, so a drastic reorganization of the educational process is needed. For example, the active use of resources of the World Wide Web by the teachers significantly increased the effectiveness of self-education of teachers of a foreign language..." (1)

On the other hand, there are some drawbacks of using technologies in lesson process, such as being confused and hesitated by devices and gadgets, being depended to social media. "... Studies have shown that smartphones and other gadgets distract students from the educational process and lead to a shorter attention span. To reverse this trend, the teacher should strive to make the learning process as interesting and effective as possible. A certain "culture" of using gadgets should be developed, and there should be mutual respect between the participants of the educational process. Of course, teachers should also limit the use of gadgets during lectures. To stop students from being distracted, instructors should take into account the potential benefits of technology and integrate it into the learning process."

Additionally, the main goal of using technology is to make everything easier, so the use of technology in education has brought a new horizon in education system. Students enjoy learning with technology and teachers have formulated more ways of integrating technology in classrooms. But another thing which every professional should take into consideration is the limitations of using modern technologies during lessons by students. To tell in nutshell, teachers should make sure that if students are using technology in the classroom does not exceed the norm and give them an idea of how to use it effectively.

“The use of modern technology in English language teaching has therefore become indispensable, especially in the wake of unprecedented developments across numerous fields and disciplines. It is essential that the education sector keep apace of the global technological revolution by adopting modern technological means such as computerization, multi-media devices, mobile phones, audio/visual effects applications, and social media, to optimize English language instruction and equip teachers to connect with classroom language learners in a systematic and advanced way. The Internet provides easy, immediate, and virtually unlimited access to software, applications, and a host of ancillary platforms and materials which can expedite English teaching and learning. While these affordances may be widely available to all, it is noted that teachers often play a key role in operating the different tools and teaching methods. Moreover, many such programs are specifically designed to promote effective English teaching whilst simultaneously increasing learner understanding and attainment of English language skills.” (2)

It is obvious that life in this modern society demands such significant skills as ability to improve themselves and develop their outlook, to comprehend the experience and practice constantly, to express their opinions and ideas clearly and confidently. In this way, technology is being helpful to develop students’ critical thinking and making decisions in problematic situations and understanding the problem that needs to be solved.

To some up, according to statistics majority of teachers (more than 50 percent) use interactive methods and information technologies in order to make their lesson

more effective and in the way of catching learners' full attention the role of modern technologies is more significant than we used to imagine. However, the effectiveness of lesson process is depending on how teacher originate the lesson and attract learners' attention by the help of innovative technologies. If students use their gadgets and mobile devices in a wrong way and waste their time during the lesson because of teacher's wrongly chosen method. Additionally, controlling the students if they are using both IT and their abilities is significant in this process, because relying too much on computers may decrease the students' individual abilities and affect the improvement of their knowledge. In the process of learning and teaching foreign languages, effectively use of high-tech will be the base and fundament on becoming a fluent user of target language.

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